

Keywords:

#marine habitat mapping, #OpenScience, #ADAMPlatform #ResearchObjects, #FAIRprinciples, #EOSCinPractice

Advancing Nordic Climate Science with Innovative EOOSC Services and Tools

Enabling Nordic climate scientists to overcome collaboration challenges and accelerate research with EOOSC services and tools

The Project Involved

RELIANCE (Research Lifecycle Management Technologies for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus Users in EOOSC) is a H2020 project funded under GA n.101017501. The project extends the research-enabling capabilities of the EOOSC with services for research lifecycle:

1) Research Objects (ROs) as the overarching mechanism to manage scientific research resources, 2) data-cubes for scalable structured data access and discovery, and 3) text mining services to extract machine-readable metadata from ROs.

RELIANCE services are co-designed with Earth Science Communities and in particular by the climate science community, represented in the project by the University of Oslo (NO) and Simula Research Laboratory (NO). Here research efforts were devoted to analysing the impact of covid-19 lockdown on air quality, and on the impact of extreme events on arctic vegetation and potential threats for local populations.

The Research Community

The Nordic climate science community comprises researchers, software engineers and students covering a broad range of relative fields such as meteorology, chemistry, biology, ecology, and, more in general, anyone with an interest in environmental data science.

The Challenge

Climate science is multidisciplinary by nature as it involves research in diverse disciplines such as physics, chemistry, biology, geology, geography, meteorology, oceanography, etc. Common tools, data and techniques used for climate include numerical models, big data analysis, AI, in-situ observations, remote sensing and laboratory experiments.

Anne Fouilloux

Anne Fouilloux, Senior Research Engineer at Simula Research Laboratory, Norway - RELIANCE

"The benefits from using EOOSC services and tools for individual researchers and small communities are immediate: it is impossible to achieve such a level of integration in a small laboratory, especially when you work in a "small" country such as Norway where skilled professionals are scarce."

To handle the huge, ever growing and distributed amounts of data involved, the software stack is diverse and complex. Also, given that the tools available are written in different programming languages (Python, Julia, R, Fortran, C, C++) and that scientists often possess different backgrounds and technical skills, this only adds to the challenge of multidisciplinary collaboration. Open Science is undoubtedly the most effective way to overcome these difficulties and EOOSC provides the framework to put it into practice.

EOOSC service or tool used

Anne Fouilloux, Senior Research Engineer at Simula Research Laboratory, Norway - RELIANCE says:

"For us it wasn't so much about using one EOOSC service or tool but the integration, communities and people."

Sharing and collaboration are made easier with the same computational environment, tools and data; avoiding "it works for me, why does it not work for you?" scenario.

We started our EOOSC journey with RoHub, aggregating artefacts into "Research Objects", with the ADAM platform for large datasets access and visualisation, and EGI Notebooks for data analysis. When storage and computational resources became problematic, we got access to larger JupyterHubs through EGI-ACE and C-SCALE projects.

EOOSC is an endless journey where practitioners thrive and push the boundaries of science and technology.

Useful tips & tricks

As researchers, if you think that you cannot implement EOOSC services and tools: you are wrong! In the RELIANCE project (<https://www.reliance-project.eu/>), RoHub (<https://reliance.rohub.org/>), the ADAM platform (<http://reliance.adamplatform.eu>), the Text-mining services (<https://reliance.expertcustomers.ai/>) are co-designed. This is usually true for all the EOOSC services and tools and your feedback is more than welcome!

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EOSC integrates many services and tools, which can seem overwhelming at the beginning. Authenticating to EOSC services and tools with your ORCID identifier is the best approach in our opinion.

A good approach for newcomers would be to identify the biggest bottleneck in their day-to-day work and find the EOSC service that could overcome it: start simple, small and then grow.

Bear in mind that those who develop and deploy services and tools are not end-users: be gentle with yourself and others. Finding another researcher using EOSC, even if working on different scientific fields, is usually the way to go.

Benefits and impact

The benefits from using EOSC services and tools for individual researchers and small communities are immediate: it is impossible to achieve such a level of integration in a small laboratory, especially when you work in a "small" country such as Norway where skilled professionals are scarce. Before, we were wasting a lot of time moving large amounts of data from one site to another (HPC to cloud to laptop). Access to ARCO (Analysis Ready Cloud Optimized) data through easy-to-use compute and storage resources such as Jupyter Notebooks significantly improved our daily routine.

Collaboration is fast and easy: data, compute and storage are always there and accessible to all. Using Research Objects (ROs) to aggregate everything we use and produce (data, software, videos, documents, etc.) changed our mindset and sped up our work. Rather than writing irrelevant Data Management Plans (DMPs), we used RO as our DMP and created regular snapshots to capture the entire life cycle of our research project. When the time to publish comes, we are ready and can share the ROs in our paper.

We are more visible (our research is more re-used and not only because it is fully reproducible), have more (and more diverse) collaborators and access to more efficient services and tools, and we also learned to be mindful when sharing (FAIR and CARE principles). Finally, we understand the role we can play to shape EOSC and benefit from it.

Useful material related to this story

reliance-project.eu

Why do I need EOSC?

EOSC plays an important role for our small community: we can push the limits of the possible and as small as we are we can think big! There is no way back: we cannot imagine having to download, prepare data and the needed computational environments locally and by ourselves, and the time involved in trying to share our work with all our collaborators.

For example, when we needed larger amounts of compute & storage to run machine learning algorithms to study the impact of extreme events on arctic vegetation (see RO titled "Vegetation browning in Troms and Finnmark (Norway)" (<https://w3id.org/ro-id/3ed30e69-fb38-4045-bd34-2fa907d12353>), a customised deployment of the Pangeo (<https://pangeo.io/>) machine learning notebook (<https://github.com/pangeo-data/pangeo-docker-images>) was made available through collaboration with EGI-ACE and C-SCALE.

On-boarding new community members is also easier. For instance, students do not need to reinvent the wheel: we point them to relevant executable Research Objects they reproduce and build upon. The learning curve is smoother. The RO titled "OCTOPUS project - exploring aerosol-Cloud inTeractiOns in CMIP6 models Using joint-histograms" (<https://w3id.org/ro-id/dd948b04-bfa4-44b0-814b-19f7daff6b8c>) by Adele Zaini is a good example.

Another clear benefit from EOSC is when you get a new job at another institution (as many researchers do): you can still be authenticated to the same services and tools with your unique ORCID identifier and continue to collaborate and work.

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Across disciplines

Working across disciplines is also facilitated by EOSC services and tools. Here is an example: our climate community focused on the impact of the lockdown on air quality (<https://w3id.org/ro-id/53aa90bfc593-4e6d-923f-d4711ac4b0e1>) while the Sea Monitoring community from RELIANCE did a similar study but analysed the water quality (<https://w3id.org/ro-id/0869e396-3733-4aff-8fb2-94c8937b28aa>).

The two original ROs are fully reproducible and reusable so it was fairly easy to combine the two studies to derive a new Jupyter notebook as demonstrated in the executable RO titled "Changes in air quality and water quality during the Covid-19 Lockdown in the Venice Lagoon (<https://w3id.org/ro-id/998dccd6-7192-4d88-af39-6018c71e6bdf>).

Open Science is a process and thanks to EOSC, we understood that making our research accessible to everyone is not necessarily difficult but it is very different from what we were told: it is a lot about people and communities of practice play an important role.

For instance, agreeing on and following clear guidelines for writing modular and reusable Jupyter Notebooks make executable Research Objects much more reusable. This is why we have teamed up with the Environmental Data Science book (EDS book, <https://edsbook.org>), a pan-european community-driven resource that enables researchers to co-design, collaboratively and openly review, and curate interactive, shareable and reproducible executable notebooks.

Useful material related to this story

reliance-project.eu

Limitations and future improvement

Tools and services are not meant to be static: they need to evolve with researchers' needs. It should not be any different for EOSC but we feel that the sustainability of the EOSC services and tools are not always clear.

Engaging and on-boarding researchers on EOSC require long-term sustainability of the tools and services provided, taking into account that future needs will emerge and will have to be taken care of.

Interoperability of the EOSC services and tools outside Europe is also important: the goal is not to create a bigger silo and isolate European researchers that can use EOSC from others. Open Science cannot be realised with Europe only. We suggest dropping the E and think about a new chapter e.g. OSC "Open Science Cloud"!

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